

OP10. PEGYLATED LIPID-BASED NANOCARRIERS FOR THE TREATMENT OF RETINOPATHIES: DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Age-related retinal diseases (ARRD) are among the leading causes of blindness worldwide, and their prevalence is expected to rise as the population ages. Hence, it is critical to develop new non-invasive treatment options to avoid the frequent intraocular injections to the posterior segment of the eye.

In this study, a topical ophthalmic drug delivery system was developed to promote interaction with the ocular surface and enhance penetration to intraocular tissues. Specifically, PEGylated lipid-based nanocarriers (LN) enriched with monoolein (MO@LN) and phytantriol (PHY@LN) were evaluated regarding their physicochemical properties (size, polydispersity index, zeta potential, stability, and thermodynamic behavior) using dynamic and electrophoretic light scattering. Optimized MO@LN and PHY@LN were also characterized *in vitro* for their encapsulation efficiency of resveratrol, for their ocular irritation potential using the Hen's egg test on the chorioallantoic membrane (HET-CAM), and for their hemocompatibility. Finally, MO@LN and PHY@LN were incorporated (soaking method) in contact lenses (CL) made of four different materials, and their impact on CL transmittance, thickness, and power was tested.

Both MO@LN and PHY@LN showed suitable physicochemical properties (< 300 nm; > +50 mV; PDI < 0.3; stable for 4 weeks) for a balanced interaction with the corneal surface and penetration along the eye. Moreover, the encapsulation of RSV was high (> 85 %) for both LN, and they neither caused irritation in chicken embryos nor promoted hemolysis of erythrocytes. CL intrinsic properties were not significantly altered with LN incorporation. Overall, MO@LN and PHY@LN seem promising drug delivery systems for the treatment of retinopathies.

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